

D1.2 Project Public Launch

WP1 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

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PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

PROJECT DETAILS

Project Title	On-Demand Bioresorbable OptoElectronic System for In-Vivo and In-Situ Monitoring of Chemotherapeutic Drugs
Project Acronym	RESORB
Call Identifier	Horizon-EIC-2021-Pathfinder Open-01
Grant Agreement No.	1010469463
Duration	36
Project Start Date	April 1 st , 2022
Project Website	www.resorb-project.eu

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No	2 – D1.2
Deliverable Title	Project public launch
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Contributing Partners	/
Nature	DEC: Websites
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Contributors	/
Reviewers	Daniela Giuliani, Elisabetta Mazzotta
Delivery Date to EC	M2 – May 31 st , 2022

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online)	v
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
EU classified	EU classified — RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
0.1	15.05.2022	Giuseppe Barillaro	First Release
0.2	22.05.2022	Giuseppe Barillaro	Update
0.3	26.05.2022	Daniela Giuliani	Internal Review
0.4	26.05.2022	Elisabetta Mazzotta	Internal Review
1.0	27.05.2022	Giuseppe Barillaro	Revision

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GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Extended Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed in this Deliverable are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the Project Public Launch is to leverage a number of open access platforms to inform the general public, scientific community, industrial professionals, about the RESORB project, vision, aim, and results.

To inform about the RESORB project and activities a Project Website, ResearchGate page, and Twitter account were set up openly available to public. Moreover, to make the project immediately recognizable to the public an original logo was created that represents the visual identity of RESORB.

The RESORB website, ResearchGate page, and Twitter account are living document throughout the entire duration of the project and will be actively maintained and updated.

2. WEBSITE

The website of RESORB is now alive at the following link: www.resorb-project.eu

The website contains several pages, namely:

Home, contains images and news about the project results

Project, explains the project aim, vision, and impact

Partners, highlights consortium partners, countries involved and major skills

Publications, showcases the publications of the consortium done within RESORB

News & Events, highlights news and events of the RESORB project

Contact, provide details of the main contact persons

3. LOGO

An original logo has been created for the project to provide a visual identity of RESORB that is easily recognized and to be used in documentation, presentation, news.

4. RESEARCHGATE PAGE

A RESORB's ResearchGate page has been created under the account of the PC of the project to inform the scientific community about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The image is a screenshot of the ResearchGate project page for RESORB. At the top, there is a teal navigation bar with the ResearchGate logo, a search bar, and a "Discover by subject area" button. On the right side of the bar are "Join for free" and "Log in" buttons. Below the navigation bar, the project title "RESORB: On-Demand Bioresorbable OptoElectronic System for In-Vivo and In-Situ Monitoring of Chemotherapeutic Drugs" is displayed, along with the name of the project leader, Giuseppe Barillaro. To the right of the title, there are statistics for updates (1 new), recommendations (0 new), followers (0 new), and reads (5 new). Below the title, the project goal is described: "Goal: RESORB - an EIC PathFinder Open project funded by the EC - envisions in-vivo bioRESORBable chemical sensing systems, where electrical and optical devices, power and light sources, chemical receptors - made out of materials that fully dissolve with biologically benign...". A "Show details" link is provided. Below the goal, there is a "Project log" section with a "Follow" button. The project log contains two entries: one where Giuseppe Barillaro added an update about the kickoff meeting on May 2nd, 2022, and another where he added a project goal. Each entry includes a share button and the number of reads.

5. TWITTER ACCOUNT

A RESORB's Twitter account has been created to inform the general public, but also scientific community and industrial professional, about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The image shows a screenshot of the RESORB Twitter profile. The profile header includes the name 'RESORB' with a '1 Tweet' indicator, a search bar, and a list of suggested accounts to follow: Virgilio Mattoli (@VMattoli), Andrea Pucci Lab (@apucci73), and Marcelle Machluf's Lab (@MachlufLab). The profile bio states: 'On-Demand Bioresorbable OptoElectronic System for In-Vivo and In-Situ Monitoring of Chemotherapeutic Drugs - an EIC Pathfinder Open project funded by the EC'. A tweet from May 24 reads: 'We envision in-vivo bioRESORBable chemical sensing, where electrical and optical devices, power and light sources, chemical receptors - made out of materials that fully dissolve with biologically benign byproducts in biofluids - will be developed and integrated for drug tracking.' The right sidebar shows trending topics for Italy, including #RomaFeyenoord (19.1K Tweets) and #strage.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY/REFERENCES

- RESORB Grant Agreement and its Annexes
- RESORB Consortium Agreement and its Annexes